

Large and small educational cards

The **lifeforce** educational cards consist of large, colour-coded dividers that introduce each unit/topic. These are followed by large cards (110 cards) and small cards (90 cards), with the front and back side designed and colour-coded, and with the corresponding colour differentiation of the module they belong to. The small cards were developed for students and the large cards for teachers. All small cards are in dyslexia-friendly font so that they are readable by all pupils, including children with learning disabilities.

They are divided into three main groups relating to the BEGIN the MIDDLE and END of the **lifeforce** course structure and they consist of thematic units.

The first three introductory cards deal with:

Lesson Structure (BEGINNING, MIDDLE, END)

Bloom's Taxonomy (Suggested questions and activities for LOTS: Level 1: Remember, Level 2: Understand, Level 3: Apply and HOTS: Level 4: Analyze, Level 5: Evaluate, Level 6: Create) and

Universal Design for Learning (UDL: activities to provide multiple means of Engaging, Representing and Action-Expressing knowledge).

The "**lifeforce Begin**" concerns a) the summary of the course in general and b) the main idea of the "Begin" of the course and how teachers can practically proceed with it. More specifically, it refers to the Lifeforce Principles & the warm-up/preparation lessons for the main themes of the program.

The "**lifeforce Main**" talks about the variety of options teachers have for the main part of the lessons to build children's basic knowledge of CPR information through many different topics. In particular, it details how the following topics can be implemented in the classroom.

Body Anatomy*

- Vocabulary
- Social-Emotional skills**
- Breathing games*
- **lifeforce** BLS Algorithm
- Foreign Body Airway Obstruction
- **lifeforce** BLS scenarios
- **lifeforce** Music (Songs, music activities - games)**
- **lifeforce** BLS Yoga poses & games*
- Language-Communication skills
- Cognitive-Perceptual skills

Body anatomy (learning and games)

The teacher uses compound verbs to accompany each body part, showing/illustrating with their own body which part they are referring to. The main aim is for the children to associate each body part with the word that means it.

Vocabulary (18 words)

The aim of the activities is to acquire, integrate and generalize the new specialized vocabulary so that pupils can use it functionally in all communication situations, especially in emergencies.

Social and Emotional Skills Cards (SES)

Emotion cards

These are 4 large cards that are color-differentiated. Each color corresponds to a self-regulation zone. On one side of each card a basic emotion is depicted and on the other side 4 emotions corresponding to the same self-regulation zone, The Emotion cards are used in two ways: 1) for emotional recognition and 2) for training in self-regulation zones.

"Fight-Flight-Freeze" cards

The 3 large "Fight - Flight - Freeze" reaction cards depict the reaction on one side and related questions on the other. They are an essential component of social and emotional skills training, because they are inextricably linked to dealing with crisis situations. Children learn to recognize the mechanism that is automatically activated for their survival both by observing their body and their thoughts.

Social and Emotional Skills Scenarios (SES) cards

These are 8 large cards with social-emotional skills scenarios on the front side and short descriptions with related questions on the other side. The scenarios are inspired by real-life events that both children and adults face. These scenarios are an opportunity for students to improve their management of situations they experience in the present and/or to prepare for future life experiences.

Breathing games

It is also a fun way for the students to gain knowledge and practical experience (Breathing Distinction Game) on the different breathing types (normal, slow, fast, agonal and noisy). With the help of the senses they play breathing games (look, listen and feel). Steps which are included in the algorithm stage to check for normal breathing.

lifeforce BLS algorithm cards

These cards are meant to teach the **lifeforce** BLS algorithm Stages and Steps

Chain of survival. Introductory card for BLS

BLS cards

There is one Divider card per stage with colour coding. Consequently, there are eight divider cards in total. On the front, there is the name of the stage and the corresponding illustration. On the back are listed all the steps that belong to the stage.

There is one large cards per stage. On the large cards, all questions belonging to the particular stage are listed, which are also included on the Small cards (pupils cards). First the questions from Step 1 card with the indication S1 are listed, then the questions of Step 2 card (S2) and so on. Also, the respective Bloom's level has been added after the questions with the suffices L1, L2, L3, L4, L5 or L6.

Of the small cards, one card exists per (nearly every) step. On the front of the small cards there is an illustration, suitable for the respective step and the description of the step. On the back of each small card there are three questions, which relate to the corresponding step. The first question is of lower order thinking skills (LOTS) from levels 1-3 (Remember, Understand, Apply) of Bloom's taxonomy. Questions two and three are questions that test higher order thinking skills (HOTS) from levels 4-6 (Analyse, Evaluate, Create) of Bloom's taxonomy.

BLS Scenario cards

They consist of 4 BLS scenario cards. One side of the cards shows the scenarios and the other side shows their description. They are followed by a large card with questions corresponding to each stage of the **lifeforce** BLS algorithm and coded L1-L6 according to Bloom's taxonomy.

Two scenarios are for ages 6-8. These scenarios are very close to the children's real experiences and correspond to the place where the education is based, in order to avoid confusion: the school is the main element.

The other two scenarios are for ages 8-10. These scenarios are very close to children's real experiences, but go a step further by including public spaces in the town/village, not only dedicated to children - as is the case with playgrounds - and the home as a place where they spend their time much more independently.

Airway obstruction by a foreign body

Included as an addendum to the **lifeforce** BLS algorithm to demonstrate the extension of **lifeforce** to other First Aid topics other than Basic Life Support. It is demonstrated using cause and effect, from two pairs of cards relating to obstruction and complete airway obstruction by a foreign body.

lifeforce BLS Yoga poses

Consisting of 8 large cards depicting the 8 **lifeforce** BLS-Algorithm Yoga poses. On the front of the card is a picture showing the name and the final result of the pose. The other side of the card is followed by a detailed description of how the children will come to each pose. The children, using the kids yoga posture technique, going through a sequence of movements, will end up performing all the steps of the BLS algorithm, each in order.

lifeforce Music cards

They contain the five songs created for the **lifeforce** programme. The songs as well as the musical activities included in the teacher and student cards have as their main goal the memorization of the steady beat of 110-120 b/m (for CPR) as well as the memorization of the specific steps (actions) that will must be followed by the students in the correct order and without delays. In this context, the songs can function as mnemonic aids, as a means to manage stress, but at the same time as amplifiers and regulators of emotions.

Language and Communication skills cards

In the **lifeforce** programme, young children are encouraged to use the small Language and Communication cards. The aim of the activities contained in the cards is for children to further develop their communication and language skills so that they are able to understand, learn and apply the information in all the steps of the **lifeforce** - BLS algorithm and in the topics of the curriculum.

Perceptual and Cognitive skills cards

Through activities that proposed train the pupils in perceptual and cognitive skills, which are relevant to learn and to automate the **lifeforce** Basic Life Support Algorithm. These skills are the primary skills the human brain uses to read, memorize, perceive, process, think, learn, reason, pay attention and move the muscles of bodies.

The "**lifeforce Lesson-End**" is about ways for the teachers to gradually end the lesson so that children physically and mentally decompress. In specific, it uses memory and concentration games, relaxation games and reflection plus team goals.